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conect4children (COLlaborative Network for European Clinical Trials For Children)

WP5 – Data coordinating
centre and data quality
standards

D5.7 Report and recommendations to leverage the potential of data sharing between paediatric clinical trials and EHRs

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Abstract

The conect4children (c4c) project¹, funded through the European Commission Innovative Medicines Initiative programme has a vision to create “Better Medicines for babies, children and young people through a Pan-European Clinical Trial Network”². One strand of c4c work has focussed on the standardization, interoperability, and reusability of data. The reuse of electronic health records (EHR) data to improve the efficiency (speed and cost) of paediatric clinical trials is one of the active areas of investigation.

A fundamental prerequisite for the success of reusing EHR data for any type of clinical study (whether it be interventional or observations) is the routine collection of relevant data items by clinicians caring for paediatric patients who are not, at the time of routine data collection, enrolled in any form of clinical research. This boils down to a fundamental question of whether routinely collected clinical data is suitable as a background historic resource for the design and conduct of these types of study.

This deliverable reports on a proof-of-concept study to explore that question, for two types of clinical studies in two disease areas, using a sample of hospitals that routinely care for paediatric patients with those conditions.

¹ <https://conect4children.org/>

² Turner, M.A., Hildebrand, H., Fernandes, R.M. et al. The conect4children (c4c) Consortium: Potential for Improving European Clinical Research into Medicines for Children. *Pharm Med* 35, 71–79 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40290-020-00373-6>

1. Contents

1.1. Introduction

A major challenge to the conduct of paediatric clinical trials is finding eligible patients in sufficient numbers to make a proposed trial viable. Further challenges exist in trial planning and feasibility, this is especially the case in rare disease areas, which are inevitably often studied in children. The classical patient recruitment pipeline includes sending candidate eligibility criteria to the sites of known investigators in a disease area for them to estimate the number of likely eligible patients. This helps to confirm that the criteria will lead to a viable trial (protocol feasibility) and indicates the likely distribution of recruitable patients and therefore which sites might be most appropriate to include in the study (site selection).

Despite the advanced adoption of EHR systems, many of these patient estimates are made on the basis of expert judgement and simplistic chart reviews and are therefore error prone^[1]. They can be over or underestimates, and there might be patients who are eligible but who are not “discovered” during recruitment and so are never invited to participate.

The drawback of launching a study that might not recruit enough patients can bring many challenges, the study may fail or face significant delays - resulting in further delays for treatment access for children. Alternatively, the trial protocol may need to be amended to modify those criteria and enlarge the candidate pool of eligible patients, which carries a significant expense and is more challenging with small populations such as paediatric patients.^[2] This is also not practical in paediatric studies which tend to have smaller populations. Some sites might rarely or never recruit a patient for a study which also presents an avoidable cost in site preparation.

There has been important multinational research over the past 15 years that has demonstrated the added value of utilising hospital EHRs to predict eligible patient numbers more accurately, with consequent trial efficiency and cost benefits, without prejudicing the confidentiality of the patient data within each EHR system^{[3][4]}. Technology products based on this research are now on the market and scaling up their deployment networks^[For example 5,6].

1.2. Applications of reused EHR data

Applications for the use of EHRs for clinical trial-type applications include (1) classical two arm trials comprising an intervention arm and a control arm, both recruited to prospectively (2) generating comparator arms from a non-recruited but observed comparable population that can serve as control groups in trials where patient populations are scarce, (3) post-marketing surveillance (PMS) or safety studies for long-term effects of existing drugs in the market, and (4) having a potential recruitment pool for future clinical trials.

Because of the rarity of eligible patients (particularly paediatric patients), the second of these models, using a real-world control arm, is attractive because it is only necessary to actively recruit patients for the interventional arm of a clinical study, and to rely upon a population derived from EHR patients to be used as a control arm. The control group of patients are usually case matched (i.e. matched pairs) to correspond to the intervention arm patients using the same eligibility criteria.

Not all clinical trials are interventional, i.e. involving the administration of a novel medicine or clinical procedure. Some are observational, utilizing longitudinal data to study the course of a disease and the effectiveness of different existing standards of care and care pathways. Observational studies still rely upon a similar case finding methodology but look to access longitudinal (historic) data as well as following up patients prospectively without interfering in their treatment. Another type of non-interventional research is the conduct of clinical safety studies, which monitor for the occurrence of adverse events in patients taking existing

treatments, including new treatments, in order to better understand the prevalence and profile of adverse events and side effects. EHRs can be an important source for providing longitudinal data as well as a log for adverse events.

The research to demonstrate the value of using hospital EHRs to improve clinical trial design and conduct has almost all been based on work undertaken on adult clinical trial protocols and therefore case finding adult patients ^[7]. There has not been work on an equivalent scale to adult studies, to verify the reuse of hospital EHRs for paediatric clinical trials. The EU Patient-centric clinical trial Platforms ((EU-PEARL, <http://eu-pearl.eu>) project ^[8], funded through the European Commission Innovative Medicines Initiative programme, has examined the feasibility and practical approaches that could be taken to establish longitudinal observational cohorts in four disease areas, including neurofibromatosis that is most often studied in children ^[9]. Its primary objective was to develop and validate a methodology for conducting (multi-arm) platform trials. Platform trials may contain a large observational cohort fulfilling a set of eligibility criteria documented within a master protocol for that disease area. As part of its method, EU PEARL has designed observational clinical study protocols and to determine the longitudinal data that would be of greatest value to prioritise collecting ^[10].

Given the resources and time available for this research it was not considered realistic to investigate the feasibility of utilising EHRs to establish a recruitment pool (longitudinal cohort) of potentially eligible patients to future trials. To calculate patient numbers for such a pool would require queries on EHR data as would be undertaken to recruit into an intervention study. This would have required a combination of ethics approvals, consent, data protection and information security measures on top of a technology capability that was beyond the scope of this investigation. Hence, the focus remained on the other two applications.

Research Question

To what extent do specialist centres treating children routinely collect data that might be re-used when recruiting or conducting a paediatric clinical trial:

- as a real world comparator arm
- as a background for safety studies

1.3. Methods

This section explains the methodology undertaken, summarized first here.

1. Confirm the clinical research use cases to focus on.
2. Confirm the example disease areas to focus on.
3. Examine samples of relevant study protocols, looking especially at eligibility criteria, extract data items and validate with clinical / patient experts as being relevant to a RWD study.
4. Consolidate as a high value data set across these use cases and convert into an online survey.
5. Select clinical sites to verify data capture of these data items in the data dictionary of their EHR systems and perform the survey of the data dictionary existence of the data items.

The work to develop the use cases and to develop the data item inventory (steps 1-4) started in June 2022 and took until October 2023 to formulate the site survey instrument. The site recruitment and onboarding (step 5) took place from January to March 2024, the survey itself ran until April 2024.

1. Confirm the clinical research use cases (study types) to focus on

The research team in consultation with the c4c project leadership opted to examine the availability of routinely collected EHR data that could be used as longitudinal observational data for either a control arm population or for a clinical safety study.

This investigation therefore sought to establish whether the EHR systems, at a number of clinical sites across Europe, had the capability to capture the data items that would ideally be needed for these two study types, preferably as data in a structured and coded form. It was not possible to examine the records of actual patients, even in aggregated or anonymised form, in order to establish frequency distributions of data item values or to estimate patient numbers. Therefore, GDPR principles did not apply to this research.

2. Confirm the example disease areas to focus on

Two clinical conditions affecting paediatric patients were selected to focus the investigation. Neurofibromatosis (NF) is a rare disease diagnosed in children, in whom most clinical research studies are therefore conducted. Atopic dermatitis (AD) is less rare, but an important condition for treatment innovation in which safety studies might be undertaken in children. In both cases these were the consensus of a group of experts within the data-oriented work package of the c4c project. This selection was entirely pragmatic based on the availability of expertise, as the objective was only to pilot this study with a couple of illustrative examples.

3. Examine samples of relevant study protocols, looking especially at eligibility criteria, extract data items and validate with clinical / patient experts as being relevant to a RWD study

A team of neurofibromatosis experts from both contributing projects c4c and EU PEARL, along with experts from Sanofi and the University of Cork, examined the NF master protocol developed in EU PEARL ^[10] and extracted from these the data items that were cited in the protocol either as eligibility criteria or as important data items to routinely collect, and from this derived a data item inventory for this investigation. The initial inventory was not filtered or prioritized but extracted in its entirety and comprised 70 data items.

Because there was no equivalent prior master protocol for clinical safety studies, two c4c investigators working within Novartis retrieved a portfolio of their recent non-confidential clinical safety study protocols (across multiple therapeutic areas) and similarly extracted the data items that were in common between these protocols, in effect replicating the methodology that had been used by the neurofibromatosis team during EU PEARL. This initial inventory was also not filtered or prioritised but extracted in its entirety and comprised 92 data items.

Each list was initially kept separate, and in each case three clinicians and two patients were asked to independently review the data element inventory to mark the ones that they believed would be most relevant to be collected during clinical encounters or would be used in their opinion for a real-world data study. In practice the experts largely agreed with each other, and de-prioritised very few data items. In retrospect, it is likely that this review step could have been avoided.

4. Consolidate as a high value data set across these use cases, and convert into an online survey

The two inventories were then combined and de-duplicated. Inevitably a number of data items relating to demographics, family history, laboratory and radiology investigations had overlaps, although their values might differ. For example, both inventories sought family history but one looked for a family history of allergic or atopic conditions, the other of neurological conditions.

The process of de-duplicating and combining data items was undertaken through several iterations by the work package experts in both conditions, and more general clinical research and informatics experts, through teleconference workshops.

The final inventory of 113 data elements combining NF and AD comprised:

- Demographic and diagnosis items = 6
- NF specific features = 12
- AD specific features = 14
- Drug and vaccine safety = 30
- Relevant family conditions = 6
- Presence of other conditions (including in the mother) = 7
- Lifestyle information = 4
- Allergy information = 8
- Examination findings = 12
- Encounter history = 14

The data item inventory was incorporated within a web-based online survey, preceded by an introductory landing page including instructions for completing the survey and how confidentiality would be handled. The next screen captured basic information from the respondent about the type of healthcare organization, its country, and the electronic health record system in use.

The heart of the survey was structured to gather data across a range of relevant data item categories. In total, 20 different categories were included, ensuring the collection of both general and disease-specific data items. Of these, 10 categories were general and covered data applicable to both disease areas, such as demographics, allergies, and other general health indicators. These general conditions were designed to capture essential patient information that is relevant across multiple conditions. The remaining 10 categories were disease-specific, with a focus on data specific to either Atopic Dermatitis or Neurofibromatosis. This distinction ensured that condition-specific details were captured while maintaining a consistent core set of shared information across both diseases. The complete survey structure, along with the full list of categories, is provided in Annex 1.

For each data item selected for inclusion in the survey, sites were asked whether they collect the specified item within their Electronic Health Record (EHR) system. The aim was not only to determine whether the data was being collected, but also to understand how it was stored and managed. Sites were presented with several response options to describe the method of data collection, ranging from highly structured electronic formats to traditional paper-based methods.

- Within the Electronic Health Record (EHR) system, in a structured and coded format.
- Within the Electronic Health Record (EHR) system as free text.
- Within a separate electronic system, not linked to the Electronic Health Record (EHR).
- On paper charts or files.
- Not directly collected but could be derived from other Electronic Health Record (EHR) data.

In addition to these options, sites also had the possibility to indicate if the data item was not collected at all or if they were unable to answer the question.

The survey was designed and deployed using LimeSurvey, a flexible platform that facilitates the collection of survey data. LimeSurvey was selected for its ability to handle various question types, manage responses from a large number of sites, and monitor participation in real-time.

5. Select clinical sites to verify data capture of these data items in the data dictionary of their EHR systems, and perform the survey of the data dictionary existence of the data items

In order to deliver high quality paediatric clinical trials, c4c has established a Network of National Hubs (NH) and qualified hospital sites across Europe with paediatric expertise. There are 20 National Hubs across 21 Countries (the Finnish National Hub covers both Finland and Iceland). Each National Hub includes a number of linked hospital sites. Due to the number of NH and NH

sites, and the likelihood that these sites would all use different Electronic Health Record systems, the network was selected to distribute the survey.

At the c4c General Assembly on 13th May 2022, the survey proposal was introduced to NH representatives. In advance of the meeting, an invite was sent to all NH representatives to promote the opportunity to attend this meeting and give feedback on the survey proposal. Representatives from three NH attended this meeting and provided feedback on the proposal and suggestions on how to increase the number of responses. Feedback suggested that further input was needed from NHs and the research would need to highlight what the incentives are for NHs completing the survey. The main takeaway from this discussion was that there was a need to clearly explain to NHs what the benefits are for NHs in the future, if it is deemed feasible to use data collected in EHRs to support paediatric clinical trials. Other incentives included being an author within a publication on the results; reported to be more of an incentive to large hospital sites, over smaller hospitals. It was agreed in this meeting that multi-stakeholder collaboration was required to complete this survey.

The survey needed to have options for multiple people e.g. clinicians and IT managers to access and contribute to the same survey response. This would help to ensure that answers are informed and of a high quality. The survey could be partially completed and saved; the link shared with other team members to enable multi-stakeholder completion (see Figure 1). This feedback was taken on board in creating the survey.

Figure 1: Example screenshot of the data item online survey

Once the draft survey was compiled, it was sent to NH representatives from Belgium, Germany and Ireland for review, and minor changes to the layout and wording to improve its clarity were made based on their suggestions. During an annual National Hub Forum meeting, the survey proposal was introduced to a larger audience of NH representatives. It was agreed during this meeting that the survey and an accompanying letter would be sent to NH coordinators, and they would then distribute the survey to relevant sites, based on their knowledge of each local site. Another action taken to increase the chances of a high response rate was to include in the letter a short and long read explaining the purpose of the survey. Within the letter, the benefits of participating and completing the survey were outlined:

- The opportunity for your c4c NH to contribute to an important c4c deliverable.
- Recognition of your contribution in a c4c deliverable and subsequent recommendations.

- Providing data which will be used to develop recommendations for future best practice.
- You will have the option of serving as a co-author on any subsequent academic publication arising from this work.
- The opportunity for NH sites to provide real-life insight into our area of research.

The working group organizers contacted the c4c Single Point of Contact (SPoC) and asked them to circulate the letter and link to the survey. The c4c SPoC provides one email address and one online form to collect requests to c4c NHs and cascades those requests to all NHs.

Engaging stakeholders in the design and dissemination of the survey was extremely effective, listening to the feedback of National Hubs improved the accessibility and ease of the survey. There was a good response from across the c4c network of sites. Involving stakeholders in designing this kind of research is recommended and shows the strength and potential for the c4c network to be engaged in similar pieces of research in the future.

At the conclusion of the survey, the data was extracted from LimeSurvey for further analysis. The platform's export functionality enabled download of the dataset in CSV format. Prior to analysis, the data underwent a cleaning process, which involved removing incomplete or duplicate responses and addressing any missing data. For data analysis, the cleaned dataset was imported into R (version 4.4.1), a powerful statistical software. R provided the necessary tools for both descriptive and inferential statistical analyses, enabling the authors to extract meaningful insights from the survey responses.

1.4. Results

Complete surveys received

The survey was distributed through National Hub (NH) contacts, rather than to individual hospital sites. We did not have a list of specific hospital sites, as these are managed at the NH level. The survey was distributed across 19 countries, including Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom.

A total of 108 survey attempts were recorded, but only 24 complete responses were submitted. It is important to note that these 108 surveys do not necessarily correspond to 108 distinct sites. Based on analysis, it appears that several sites started the survey multiple times, likely because they needed to identify the appropriate individuals within their organization who were best suited to complete specific sections of the survey. As a result, multiple attempts may have been made before a site could finalize its response.

Countries and site frequencies

Data was collected from a variety of hospitals across Europe, providing insights into both the Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems in use and the age ranges of patients cared for at each site. A total of 24 entries were included in the survey, representing sites from 11 countries: Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Estonia, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, and Switzerland. Additionally, there was one site that completed the survey but did not specify its represented country of origin.

Switzerland and the Netherlands were the most represented countries, with each contributing respectively 5 and 4 hospital sites to the study. However, with only 24 responses overall – an average of approximately two sites per country across the 11 countries represented – this reflects a relatively low response rate.

EHR systems and their usage

The survey reveals that participating sites employ a diverse range of EHR systems, reflecting the

varied healthcare infrastructure across Europe. Notably, 6 hospitals did not report the specific EHR system they used, marked as “NA”. This might suggest that the individual completing the survey was not aware of the specific EHR system in use at their site.

The data highlights the diversity of EHR systems in use, with both large, globally recognized systems like Epic and Cerner being adopted across multiple countries, as well as regional systems like Chipsoft in the Netherlands and Costec AG in Belgium and Switzerland. The presence of in-house EHR systems at several Swiss hospitals underscores a trend where some institutions prefer greater control over their EHR systems, allowing for customization tailored to local needs.

Country	EHR systems	Frequency
Austria	PCS	1
	NA	1
Belgium	Hix	1
	PRIMUZ	1
	COSTEC AG	1
Czech Republic	NA	1
Estonia	NA	1
Ireland	Cerner	1
Italy	Trackcare	1
	NA	1
Netherlands	Chipsoft	3
	EPIC	1
Portugal	Oracle	1
	NA	1
Spain	SAP	1
	HP-HCIS	1
Switzerland	In house	2
	EPIC	2
	COSTEC AG	1
NA	EPIC	1

Table 1: Countries and frequency EHR systems used

Age ranges of patients

Sites were also asked to specify the ranges of patients they care for. Most of the sites reported providing care for neonates, with only two exceptions in the Netherlands and Spain. All hospitals surveyed provide care for children up to 12 years old, and nearly all care for children between 12 and 18 years old, reflecting a strong focus on paediatric care across Europe.

In contrast, fewer hospitals also provide care for adults (18+ years old), with adult care typically offered in paediatric hospitals that see both children and adults. This care was primarily concentrated in hospitals located in Austria, Belgium, Switzerland, and the select sites in the Netherlands. Importantly, all the hospitals that provide adult care still maintain a strong paediatric focus, ensuring that they serve minor patients as well.

Demographics and diagnosis

Data items related to demographics and diagnosis showed high consistency in structured and coded formats for essential variables like date of birth (95.83 %) and sex (95.83 %). Birth weight, paediatric diagnosis, and gestational age were less consistently collected in a structured format, with some being derived from other EHR data or recorded as free text. For paediatric diagnosis, 37.5% was recorded as free text, while only 58.33% was structured. This emphasizes variability in how general patient demographic data is managed across sites, which may affect the standardization and accessibility of critical patient information. Annex 1 provides an in-depth view of these results, and figure 2 presents the summarized data for this section.

Figure 2: Demographics and Diagnosis

Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Participants were asked questions about the presence of data items within their EHR system. Some of these data items specifically related to the case studies we were exploring: Atopic Dermatitis, Neurofibromatosis and Post-Marketing Surveillance. Within the results section of this deliverable, some sections include results for all case studies, which have been grouped and analysed together. These sections are: relevant family conditions, relevant past procedures, presence of other conditions, lifestyle and social status, allergies, current findings and encounter history. A paper will be developed based on this deliverable and further analysis will be carried out on the results.

Neurofibromatosis

Data collection for neurofibromatosis-specific variables showed substantial variation across sites. Data items like cutaneous neurofibroma, high- and low-grade glioma, and plexiform neurofibroma were primarily documented using free text or in structured and coded formats. For example, cutaneous neurofibroma was recorded in structured format at only 12.5% of sites, while 41.67% used free text, which may challenge systematic data extraction. Similarly, confirmation of NF1 diagnosis was structured in only 12.5% of cases, with a significant proportion (37.5%) of sites leaving this item unanswered, highlighting gaps in the genetic confirmation of diagnoses. Annex 1 provides a detailed breakdown, and figure 3 shows the key findings.

Figure 3: Neurofibromatosis

Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Low Grade Glioma (LGG) data

For low-grade glioma, approximately 41.66% of sites collected structured data on diagnosis and therapy, but MRI results and tumour types were mostly recorded as free text. With only 12.5% of tumour type data structured, there are significant gaps in how low-grade glioma is tracked, which may impact research and care standardization. Further insights are detailed in Annex 1, and the summarized results can be seen in figure 4.

Figure 4: Low Grade Glioma (LGG) data
 Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Optic Pathway Glioma (OPG) data

Sites reported MRI scan results for OPG in structured formats at 45.82%, but there were gaps in the use of RAPNO or Dodge criteria, with only 37.48% and 29.15%, respectively, using structured formats. The lack of systematic data capture in key diagnostic criteria may hinder cross-comparison of treatment outcomes. Annex 1 provides more in-depth information, and figure 5 summarizes these findings.

Figure 5: Optic Pathway Glioma data

Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Plexiform Neurofibroma (PN) data

For Plexiform Neurofibroma (PN) data, approximately 41.67% of sites captured information like location, therapy, and MRI scan results in free text, with only 8.34% structured. A considerable portion of data was not collected at all, making the systematic tracking of PN difficult across sites. The reliance on free-text data further complicates longitudinal patient management and outcome assessment. A more detailed analysis is available in Annex 1, and figure 6 summarizes these results.

Figure 6: Plexiform Neurofibroma data

Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Atopic dermatitis

For Atopic Dermatitis, a majority of sites captured data on symptoms like herpes simplex and folliculitis using free text formats (58.33% and 54.17%, respectively), with only small proportions of data being structured. A significant percentage of sites did not collect or provide answers for these data points, showing potential data gaps in the tracking of symptomatology. This lack of structured data may limit efficient tracking of disease progression or patient management outcomes. Additionally, specific skin-related symptoms like infected eczema and urticaria showed low rates of structured data capture. Annex 1 offers further details, and figure 7 illustrates the results.

Figure 7: Atopic Dermatitis

Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Drug and vaccine safety

Data related to drug and vaccine safety were primarily collected in structured and coded formats (over 50% for most items). Critical variables like vital signs (66.67%), medication dose (58.33%), and frequency of administration (58.33%) were consistently coded. However, some data, such as the lot number of vaccines (50%) and brand name of medication (45.83%), were captured less systematically. This disparity may pose challenges in ensuring comprehensive drug safety reporting, particularly for vaccination-related data, where incomplete records might affect safety monitoring. Further insights can be found in Annex 1, with key findings shown in figure 8.

Figure 8: Drug and Vaccine Safety

Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Relevant family conditions

Family history variables, including psychiatric disease and substance abuse, were primarily collected in structured formats, but a notable portion of data was not collected or was derived from other EHR sources. For instance, psychiatric history of the father and mother was structured in 62.49% of responses, but a substantial number of sites reported not collecting this information. This variability may affect the understanding of hereditary or environmental factors influencing disease progression in both Neurofibromatosis and Atopic Dermatitis patients. Annex 1 contains more detailed results, and figure 9 presents a summary of the findings.

Figure 9: Relevant Family Conditions
 Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Family conditions in Atopic Dermatitis

Data related to family history for Atopic Dermatitis showed that 50% of sites captured information about family members’ history of Atopic Dermatitis in a structured format. A smaller proportion of sites relied on derived or free-text data, highlighting variability in documenting familial links to the disease. Annex 1 contains a more detailed view, and figure 10 provides a visual summary.

Figure 10: Family Conditions in Atopic Dermatitis

Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Family conditions in Neurofibromatosis

For family history data related to Neurofibromatosis, approximately 54.18% of sites collected structured data, but 41.64% left these items unanswered. This suggests significant data gaps, which may limit the ability to understand the hereditary nature of the condition across families. Further details are available in Annex 1, with figure 11 summarizing the results.

Figure 11: Family Conditions in Neurofibromatosis
 Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Relevant past procedures

Data items on procedures, including the date and type of procedures performed, were predominantly collected in structured formats, though some sites left questions unanswered. Around 50% of sites captured structured procedure data, with additional entries left blank or collected on paper charts. Indications for procedures and outcomes were also largely structured (50% and 41.67%, respectively). However, gaps in reporting on the provider type and procedure indication suggest inconsistencies in documentation, which may impact procedural outcome analysis. For a more detailed view, see Annex 1 and refer to figure 12 for a summary.

Figure 12: Relevant Past Procedures

Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Presence other conditions

Multiple birth history, development delay, and psychiatric disorders related to the patient were primarily captured in structured and coded formats (41.68% for development delay), though notable gaps were present. For instance, data on birth complications was structured at 56.67% of sites, leaving a significant proportion uncollected or derived from other sources. These inconsistencies in documentation may limit the holistic view of a patient’s medical background. Annex 1 explores these aspects further, and figure 13 displays the summarized data.

Figure 13: Presence of Other Conditions
 Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Lifestyle and social status

Data related to lifestyle factors like feeding type, caregiver education, and smoking exposure showed considerable variation in how sites captured the information. For example, personal smoking history was structured in only 58.33% of responses, with a significant proportion of data either uncollected or left unanswered. These inconsistencies may limit a comprehensive understanding of lifestyle factors influencing patient outcomes. For more in-depth data, see Annex 1, and figure 14 presents the main results.

Figure 14: Lifestyle and Social Status
 Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Allergies

Collection of allergy data was highly variable. Hypersensitivity to medications was structured and coded at 50% of sites, and food allergies at 41.66%. However, a substantial proportion of data related to other allergies or confirmatory testing was uncollected or recorded as free text. This variability underscores challenges in tracking comprehensive allergy profiles across patients. Additional details can be found in Annex 1, while figure 15 summarizes these results.

Figure 15: Allergies
 Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Current findings

Clinical measurements, such as weight and blood pressure, were consistently recorded in structured and coded formats, with systolic and diastolic blood pressure structured at 68.67% of sites. Temperature, heart rate, and oxygen saturation were similarly structured at over 60% of sites, providing a reliable source of vital patient metrics. However, a small number of sites continued to rely on paper-based or free-text entries, potentially complicating patient monitoring and longitudinal data analysis. Annex 1 provides further detail, and figure 16 displays a concise summary.

Figure16: Current Findings

Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Encounter History

Dates of admission, discharge, and other encounter types were highly structured at most sites, with over 70% of responses capturing this data in coded formats. However, there were some gaps, with 16.67% of sites leaving these questions unanswered. Data related to referral sources and encounter type for primary care showed more variability, with only 50% of responses structured. These gaps may hinder a complete understanding of the patient's journey through the healthcare system. More information is provided in Annex 1, and figure 17 presents the key findings.

Figure 17: Encounter History

Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Radiotherapy: Neurofibromatosis Specific

Radiotherapy data related to neurofibromatosis was primarily structured and coded at most sites for key variables like dose (41.67%), frequency (37.49%), and start date (41.66%). However, a small proportion of data remained unstructured or uncollected, particularly regarding dose calculation methods and target volumes, which could impact standardized reporting of radiotherapy outcomes. Annex 1 provides further details, and Figure 18 shows a summary of the results.

Figure 18: Radiotherapy, Neurofibromatosis Specific
 Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

Phototherapy AD

Phototherapy data, including dosage and frequency, was primarily captured in free-text formats (41.67%) with structured entries appearing in a minority of cases (16.67%). This variability in data capture, especially for key treatment indicators, may limit the study of phototherapy efficacy across sites. A more comprehensive analysis is available in Annex 1, and the summarized findings are presented in figure 19.

Figure 19: Phototherapy, Atopic Dermatitis Specific
 Each colour represents the percentage of sites collecting the data item in a particular format

1.5. Discussion

The reuse of electronic health records for clinical research studies is now well established in adult patient populations in therapeutic areas such as oncology. The technology products and the data mapping skills needed to harness the knowledge within EHR systems for the main use cases of protocol feasibility, site selection, patient recruitment and screening are now mainstream, available commercially and there are growing deployment networks of connected hospitals, globally.

However, while the same technical solutions could be applied to paediatric trials in general, there is an anecdotal scepticism about whether the underlying EHR systems are well-designed to capture the needed information for these patient populations. Although this study included a rare disease (Neurofibromatosis) and a common paediatric condition (Atopic Dermatitis), the observations made here may be relevant to a wide range of paediatric conditions, with vaccines possibly being an exception due to their specific data requirements. The high number of responses captured as “free text” in our study suggests that EHRs may not allow for adequate structured data collection. This highlights a potential gap in their ability to collect clinically relevant information in a reusable format for research purposes.

This study, small and simple in design and scale, aimed to investigate whether routinely collected paediatric healthcare data is rich enough to be reusable for research. The investigation has used a sound methodology to develop the inventory of data items that would be of high value for observational research, real world control arms and for safety studies, in two paediatric conditions, one of which is rare (Neurofibromatosis) and one common (Atopic Dermatitis). While reasonable for a proof-of-concept study, the authors accept that this limited scope, piloted in a pragmatically selected group of European clinical investigational sites, does not present scientifically robust evidence that paediatric studies can now be designed and set up with confidence using EHR data.

Although the survey was distributed to 21 countries, only 11 provided feedback, resulting in responses from just 24 sites. This low response rate – approximately 50% of the countries replied – creates a potential bias and limits the generalizability of the study’s results. Despite these limitations, the study’s methodology could be scaled up to include a wider range of paediatric conditions and a broader geographic distribution of clinical sites. Expanding both the scope of conditions studied and the range of participating sites could help establish a more robust evidence base, with relatively low additional cost.

The authors’ intent through this investigation has been to bring greater visibility to the importance and realistic plausibility of leveraging EHR data to help tackle the challenge of the limited number of paediatric patients and the difficulty finding them when developing clinical trials. The findings of this survey suggest that data items are often available, though not always collected in a structured and coded form. It appears that administrative information may be well captured in structured systems, while more specific medical information tends to be recorded as free text. This may indicate a disparity in the training of staff responsible for inputting clinical versus administrative data, or limitations in the EHR systems themselves, which may not support the structured entry of more complex medical information. These relevant data items are often available in narrative form (such as clinic letters and discharge summaries) and maybe scattered across multiple hospital sub-systems or subject to data entry quality and compliance with EHR maintenance protocols. This can result in data being lost, inconsistently recorded, or stored in multiple systems or formats, making it difficult to harness this information efficiently for research purposes.

In addition to highlighting the importance of scaling up the evidence and confidence in EHR-informed clinical research in children and rare diseases, the authors hope that healthcare providers and clinical research organizations will advocate for the value of structured and coded data to EHR systems developers and healthcare professional organizations. The goal is to improve both the design of EHR systems and the training of staff in capturing medical information in structured and

computable data formats.

There is a clear need to increase the proportion of computable data in EHRs to facilitate its reuse for research, ultimately enhancing the feasibility of paediatric and rare disease studies. It may also be valuable to compare the use of EHRs in paediatric care to their use in adult populations. This could help assess whether paediatric data is being underserved compared to adult data, which may hinder its potential for research and clinical trial design.

1.6. Conclusion and recommendations

This deliverable reports on a pragmatic Investigation Into whether healthcare provider organisations (primarily hospitals) that are generally active in undertaking clinical research routinely collect data items on their paediatric patients that would be of high value for the design and conduct of clinical trials. This investigation has focused on two study types that are important in paediatrics, especially in rare diseases: the use of EHR data to establish a real-world comparator arm in a clinical trial, and as historical background clinical information for safety studies. Two disease areas, neurofibromatosis and atopic dermatitis, were selected as the examples to study.

24 sites from 11 countries across Europe and the c4c network completed the survey. It was found that a high proportion of the clinical data was routinely collected (apart from lifestyle data), but that a lot of the time the relevant information was in free text entries such as clinic letters, investigation reports and discharge summaries.

Given the limited scale of this investigation it is recommended that this method is replicated across more paediatric disease areas and with larger hospital site sample sizes, in order to generate more robust evidence of data availability. It would appear that natural language processing (NLP) technologies would be needed in the near future to extract coded concepts from narrative in order to have a sufficient level of completeness of data for clinical research purposes.

This investigation could be considered an early call to healthcare providers, healthcare professionals and to the developers of EHR systems to encourage the greater documentation of structured and coded entries, in order to scale up the value of the data for research. It is also likely that better quality structured and coded data could be reused by each healthcare organisation and by health systems for wider quality and safety purposes. However, it is important to find strategies for improving the proportion and quality of structured and coded EHR entries without increasing the data entry burden on clinicians.

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Annexes

Annex 1: Additional Information from Survey

Demographics and diagnose							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Date of birth	/	/	/	/	/	4,17 %	95,83 %
Sex	/	/	/	/	/	4,17 %	95,83 %
Birth weight	4,18 %	8,33 %	/	/	/	16,66 %	70,83 %
Pediatric diagnosis	/	4,17 %	/	/	/	37,5 %	58,33 %
Gestational age of birth	4,18 %	8,33 %	/	/	/	37,5 %	50 %
Date of diagnosis	/	4,17 %	/	/	/	50 %	45,83 %
Neurofibromatosis							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Cutaneous neurofibroma	37,5 %	4,17 %	4,16 %	/	/	41,67 %	12,5 %
High grade glioma	37,5 %	4,17 %	4,16 %	/	/	41,67 %	12,5 %
Low grade glioma	37,5 %	4,17 %	4,16 %	/	/	41,67 %	12,5 %
NF1 diagnosis genetically confirmed	37,5 %	12,5 %	/	4,17 %	/	33,33 %	12,5 %
Plexiform neurofibroma	37,5 %	4,17 %	4,16 %	/	/	41,67 %	12,5 %
Anterolateral bowing of the tibia	37,5 %	8,33 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,67 %	8,33 %
Distinctive issues lesions	37,5 %	8,33 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,67 %	8,33 %
Optic pathway glioma	37,5 %	8,33 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,67 %	8,33 %
Paraspinal plexiform neurofibroma	37,5 %	8,33 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,67 %	8,33 %
Pseudoarthrosis of a long bone	37,5 %	8,33 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,67 %	8,33 %
Sphenoid dysplasia	37,5 %	8,33 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,67 %	8,33 %
Genetically pathogen variant	45,83 %	8,33 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	33,33 %	4,17 %
Atopic dermatitis							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Presence of herpes simplex	29,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	54,17 %	12,5 %
Presence of folliculitits	29,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	58,33 %	8,33 %
Presence of infected eczema	29,17 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	58,33 %	8,33 %
Presence of urticaria	29,17 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	58,33 %	8,33 %
Presence of dusky erythema	29,17 %	/	8,33 %	/	/	58,33 %	4,17 %
Presence of erythematous rash	29,17 %	/	8,33 %	/	/	58,33 %	4,17 %
Presence of exacerbation of eczema	29,17 %	/	8,33 %	/	/	58,33 %	4,17 %
Presence of exacerbation of pruritus	29,17 %	/	8,33 %	/	/	58,33 %	4,17 %
Presence of nocturnal scratching	29,17 %	/	8,33 %	/	/	58,33 %	4,17 %
Presence of non-skin atopic symptoms	29,17 %	/	8,33 %	/	/	58,33 %	4,17 %
Presence of skin irritation	29,17 %	/	8,33 %	/	/	58,33 %	4,17 %
Presence of stinging	29,17 %	4,16 %	4,16 %	/	/	58,33 %	4,17 %
Presence of blisters	29,17 %	8,33 %	/	/	/	62,5 %	/
Presence of burning	29,17 %	4,17 %	8,33 %	/	/	58,33 %	/
Drug and vaccine safety							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Vital signs	16,67 %	/	/	/	4,16 %	12,5 %	66,67 %

Dose of medication	12,5 %	/	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	20,83 %	58,33 %
Frequency of administration	12,5 %	/	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	20,83 %	58,33 %
Generic name of medication	12,5 %	4,17 %	/	4,17 %	/	20,83 %	58,33 %
Imaging results	12,5 %	/	/	4,17 %	4,17 %	20,83 %	58,33 %
Route of administration	12,5 %	/	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	20,83 %	58,33 %
Start date	12,5 %	/	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	20,83 %	58,33 %
Stop date	12,5 %	/	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	20,83 %	58,33 %
Adverse drug or vaccine reactions	12,5 %	4,17 %	/	4,17 %	/	20,83 %	58,33 %
Lot number of vaccine	12,5 %	16,67 %	/	4,16 %	/	16,67 %	50 %
Brand name of medication	12,5 %	16,67 %	4,16 %	/	4,16 %	16,67 %	45,83 %
Results of development assessment	12,5 %	/	/	4,17 %	4,17 %	20,83 %	58,33 %
Date of vaccination	12,5 %	20,83 %	/	/	4,17 %	25 %	37,5 %
How the dose was calculated	20,83 %	8,33 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	20,83 %	37,5 %
Indication of medication	8,33 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	/	/	45,83 %	33,33 %
Severity of reaction	12,5 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	50 %	25 %
Date of investigation or test	12,5 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	62,5 %	20,83 %
Reasons for stopping medication (if applicable)	12,5 %	12,5 %	8,34 %	/	/	45,83 %	20,83 %
Outcome of reaction	12,5 %	/	8,34 %	4,17 %	/	58,33 %	12,67 %
Vaccine brand name	12,5 %	12,5 %	8,34 %	/	/	50 %	16,67 %
Date of onset of reaction	12,5 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	8,34 %	/	54,17 %	12,5 %
Date of resolution of reaction	12,5 %	/	12,5 %	4,17 %	/	58,33 %	12,5 %
Date of resolution, if applicable	20,83 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	4,17 %	50 %	8,33 %
Medication error	12,5 %	/	12,5 %	4,17 %	/	62,5 %	8,33 %
Reaction confirmed by health care provider	12,5 %	/	8,34 %	4,17 %	/	66,67 %	8,33 %
Treatment administered for reaction	12,5 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	4,17 %	/	62,5 %	8,33 %
Clinical sign or abnormal test results due to medication error	12,5 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	58,33 %	4,17 %
Date of error	20,83 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	4,17 %	54,17 %	4,17 %
Laboratory test results	20,83 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	/	58,33 %	4,17 %
Outcome of error	16,67 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	8,34 %	/	58,33 %	4,17 %
Relevant family conditions							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
History of psychiatric disease in the father	12,5 %	16,67 %	4,17 %	/	/	62,49 %	4,17 %
History of psychiatric disease in the mother	12,5 %	16,67 %	4,17 %	/	/	62,49 %	4,17 %
History of learning difficulty in the father	12,5 %	33,33 %	4,17 %	/	/	50 %	/
History of learning difficulty in the mother	12,5 %	33,33 %	4,17 %	/	/	50 %	/
History of substance abuse problems in the father	12,5 %	20,83 %	4,17 %	/	/	62,5 %	/
History of substance abuse problems in the mother	12,5 %	20,83 %	4,17 %	/	/	62,5 %	/
Relevant past procedure							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Date of procedure	12,5 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	50 %	41,67 %
Encounter type	12,5 %	18,75 %	8,34 %	/	/	18,74 %	41,67 %
Procedure(s) type	12,5 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	45,83 %	37,5 %
Provider type	12,5 %	29,17 %	8,33 %	/	/	12,5 %	37,5 %

Indication for the procedure	12,5 %	/	8,33 %	/	/	50 %	29,17 %
Procedure outcome	12,5 %	8,33 %	8,33 %	/	/	41,67 %	29,17 %
Presence other conditions							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Multiple births by the mother	/	8,33 %	8,33 %	/	/	58,37 %	25 %
History of development delay related to the patient	16,67 %	8,34 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,68 %	12,5 %
History of psychiatric disorder related to the patient	16,67 %	8,34 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,68 %	12,5 %
Perinatal events of the mother	4,17 %	8,33 %	8,33 %	/	/	66,67 %	12,5 %
Birth complications of the mother	4,17 %	12,5 %	8,33 %	/	/	56,67 %	8,33 %
History of substance abuse problems related to the patient	16,67 %	12,5 %	/	/	/	41,68 %	8,33 %
Pregnancy conditions of the mother	/	8,33 %	8,33 %	/	/	75,01 %	8,33 %
Lifestyle and social status							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Feeding type	4,17 %	20,83 %	/	/	/	58,33 %	16,67 %
Care givers education level	4,17 %	45,83 %	/	/	/	37,5 %	12,5 %
Personal smoking history	4,17 %	25 %	/	/	/	58,33 %	12,5 %
Infant exposure to smoking	4,17 %	33,33 %	/	/	/	54,17 %	8,33 %
Allergies							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
History of hypersensitivity to medications	16,67 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	29,17 %	50 %
Food allergies	16,67 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	41,66 %	37,5 %
Other allergies	16,67 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	54,17 %	25 %
Confirmation by a healthcare provider	16,67 %	12,5 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	4,66 %	20,83 %
Confirmatory testing	16,67 %	8,33 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	50 %	16,67 %
Conunctivitis (AD specific)	16,67 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	54,15 %	16,67 %
Exposure to aeroallergens/irritants	16,67 %	29,16 %	/	/	/	41,67 %	12,5 %
Infant exposure to food allergens	16,67 %	20,83 %	4,17 %	/	/	54,16 %	4,17 %
Current findings							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Weight	4,17 %	/	/	4,17 %	/	12,49 %	79,17 %
Diastolic blood pressure	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	18,82 %	68,67 %
Systolic blood pressure	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	18,82 %	68,67 %
The data of these measurements	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	18,82 %	68,67 %
Height (or length for babies)	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	18,82 %	68,67 %
Head circumference	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	16,65 %	66,67 %
Heart rate	4,17 %	8,34 %	/	4,17 %	/	16,65 %	66,67 %
Pulse rate	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	4,17 %	/	20,82 %	66,67 %
Temperature	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	4,17 %	/	20,82 %	66,67 %
Respiratory rate							
Oxygen saturation	4,17 %	8,34 %	/	4,17 %	/	24,98 %	58,34 %
Bacterial, viral or fungal infections (AD specific)	4,17 %	8,34 %	/	8,34 %	/	45,84 %	33,34 %
Encounter history							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not	Free text	Structured and coded

					linked to EHR		
Date of admission	16,67 %	/	/	/	/	12,5 %	70,83 %
Date of discharge	16,67 %	/	/	/	/	12,5 %	70,83 %
Date of encounter or observation	16,67 %	/	/	/	/	12,5 %	70,83 %
Encounter type: ambulatory clinic	16,67 %	/	/	/	/	12,5 %	70,83 %
Encounter type: hospital admission	16,67 %	/	/	/	/	12,5 %	70,83 %
Date of discharge	16,67 %	16,67 %	/	/	/	/	66,66 %
Date of transfer	16,67 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	16,67 %	62,49 %
If currently participating in clinical trial	12,5 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	20,84 %	62,49 %
Location of transfer	16,67 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	16,67 %	62,49 %
Provider/facility type	16,67 %	/	/	4,17 %	/	16,67 %	62,49 %
Encounter type: primary/community care	16,67 %	20,83 %	/	/	/	12,5 %	50 %
Source of referral	16,67 %	/	/	/	/	33,33 %	50 %
Encounter type: study observation	16,67 %	8,34 %	/	4,17 %	/	22,87 %	47,95 %
Type of transport	16,67 %	20,84	/	/	/	24,99 %	37,5 %
If PN is present							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Location of plexiform neurofibroma	41,67 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,65 %	8,34 %
Therapy received for plexiform neurofibroma	41,67 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,65 %	8,34 %
MRI scan results	37,5 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	4,17 %	45,83 %	4,17 %
Tumour size on MRI: longest diameter	41,67 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	/	4,17 %	37,48 %	4,17 %
Type of plexiform neurofibroma complications	41,67 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	45,82 %	4,17 %
If LGG is present							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Diagnosis	41,66 %	4,17 %	/	4,17 %	/	37,5 %	12,5 %
Therapy received	41,66 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,66 %	8,34 %
MRI scan results	37,49 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	4,17 %	45,83 %	4,17 %
Tumour location	41,66 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	/	41,66 %	8,34 %
Tumour type	41,66 %	4,17 %	/	4,17 %	/	37,5 %	12,5 %
RAPNO criteria	41,66 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	8,34 %	41,66 %	/
If OPG is present							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
MRI scan results	37,5 %	/	4,17 %	/	4,17 %	45,82 %	8,34 %
Dodge criteria	41,67 %	12,5 %	8,34 %	/	8,34 %	29,15 %	/
RAPNO criteria	41,67 %	4,17 %	8,34 %	/	8,34 %	37,48 %	/
Relevant family conditions related to Neurofibromatosis							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Neurofibromatosis related to the father	41,64 %	/	4,18 %	/	/	54,18 %	/
Neurofibromatosis related to the mother	41,64 %	/	4,18 %	/	/	54,18 %	/
Neurofibromatosis related to the siblings	41,64 %	/	4,18 %	/	/	54,18 %	/
Relevant family conditions related to Atopic Dermatitis							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded

Atopic dermatitis related to siblings	25 %	4,18 %	4,18 %	/	/	50 %	4,18 %
Atopic dermatitis related to the father	25 %	4,18 %	4,18 %	/	/	50 %	4,18 %
Atopic dermatitis related to the mother	25 %	4,18 %	4,18 %	/	/	50 %	4,18 %
Phototherapy – Atopic dermatitis specific							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Dose	41,67 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	37,49 %	16,67 %
Dose calculation method	41,67 %	12,5 %	/	/	/	29,16 %	16,67 %
Frequency	41,67 %	8,34 %	/	/	/	33,32 %	16,67 %
Indication	41,67 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	41,66 %	12,5 %
Start date	41,67 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	41,66 %	12,5 %
Stop date	41,67 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	41,66 %	12,5 %
Target area	41,67 %	8,34 %	/	/	/	37,49 %	12,5 %
Outcome	41,67 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	45,82 %	8,34 %
Side effect	41,67 %	4,17 %	/	/	/	45,82 %	8,34 %
Radiotherapy – Neurofibromatosis specific							
	No answer	Not collected	Derived from other EHR data	Paper charts	Separate system not linked to EHR	Free text	Structured and coded
Dose	41,67 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	41,67 %	12,5 %
Dose calculation method	41,67 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	33,32 %	12,5 %
Frequency	41,67 %	/	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	37,49 %	12,5 %
Route of administration	41,67 %	/	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	37,49 %	12,5 %
Start date	41,67 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	41,66 %	12,5 %
Indication	41,67 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	41,66 %	8,34 %
Outcome	41,67 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	41,66 %	8,34 %
Stop date	41,67 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	41,66 %	8,34 %
Target volume	41,67 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	4,17 %	/	37,48 %	8,34 %
Side effects	41,67 %	/	4,17 %	/	/	50 %	4,17 %

History of change

Version 4.0 dated 23/10/2024	
Section changed	Description of change
None	None